

Effect of Matrix on Corrosion Resistance of FRP

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve corrosion resistance of glass roving cloth reinforced polyesters, a commercial orthophthalic polyester was modified with various additives. A few additives were found to be effective to improve the flexural strength of FRP before and after immersion in boiling water.

As the matrix seemed to be responsible for the corrosion resistance of FRP, 4-types of polyesters were examined by the immersion in boiling water and by the heating in a pressure cooker. As the results of the immersion the tensile strength of the polyesters reduced remarkably, while the fracture toughness of them remained almost unchanged. The flexural strength of chopped strand mat-polyesters decreased after immersion in boiling water. The extent of the reduction in the strength of immersed FRP, was smaller than that of neat polyester.

The accelerating degradation of FRP by use of a pressure cooker was compared with that of boiling water immersion. The immersion in boiling water for 24 hr approximately corresponded to 8-hr heating in the pressure cooker.

INTRODUCTION

Recently the needs for FRP structural parts in the field of corrosive environments such as containers for water, chemical tanks and chemical plants have been increased remarkably. FRP has many advantages over metal: relatively light, strong and rustless. In an corrosion resistant FRP, it is generally considered that the glass fibers mainly support the load and the matrix is responsible for the corrosion. Therefore, to improve the corrosion resistance of the matrix is really important. When a FRP is allowed to stand in humid environments, it absorbs water and consequently some mechanical properties of the FRP decrease. The absorption of water into FRP and the reduction of the mechanical properties increase with increase in temperature.

A commercial orthophthalic polyester was modified with various additives, in order to improve the corrosion resistance of FRP. These additives were allyl monomers, vinyl monomers and hydrophobic chemicals. Allyl and vinyl monomers must react with the polyester in the curing process. The addition of hydrophobic chemicals was expected to protect FRP against water. Several additives were

found to improve the flexural strength of FRP before and after immersion in boiling water.

In order to evaluate the durability of FRP in humid environments for a long time, the accelerating degradation of 4-types of polyesters was investigated by the immersion in boiling water both at atmospheric pressure and at slightly higher pressure by use of a pressure cooker. The tensile strength of the immersed resins decreased, and the reduction in the strength was depended on the type of the resin. However, the fracture toughness of the immersed resin was almost unchanged. The chopped strand mat-polyester laminates prepared by these resins were examined for the flexural strength before and after immersion.

The acceleration of FRP degradation by the use of a pressure cooker over conventional boiling water immersion was found to be roughly 3-4 times. Therefore, the pressure cooker was an effective tool for the immersion test of FRP with saving in time and energy.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The polyesters used were Epolac G-180, Epolac N350-L Epolac RF-1001 and Epolac RF-1 (Japan Catalitic Chemical Industry Co. Ltd.). These resins were chosen as representatives of orthophthalic polyester (O-resin), isophthalic polyester (I-resin), vinyl ester (V-resin) and bisphenol-A polyester (B-resin), respectively. In the cases of O- and I-resins, the curing agents used were 1 phr of MEKPO (55 %) and 0.5 phr of Co naphthenate (0.6 %). V- and B-resins were cured with 2 phr of MEKPO and 0.5 phr of Co naphthenate. The polyester was mixed with curing agents, the mixture was degassed and casted between two glass plates. The cured neat polyester (6 mm thick) was postcured at 100°C for 2 hr. The additives used for the modification of O-resin were allyl glycidyl ether (AGE, 5 phr), diallyl phthalate (DAP, 5 phr), glycidyl methacrylate (GMA, 5 phr), methyl methacrylate (MMA, 5 phr), styrene (St, 5 phr), paraffin liquid (Para, 1 phr), and white vaseline (Vase, 2 phr).

The glass roving cloth and the glass chopped strand mat used were REW-580M and EM-450G-5 (Nippon Glass Fiber Co. Ltd.), respectively. All the glass fiber reinforced laminates were fabricated by the hand-lay-up technique. The thickness of the FRP plate was adjusted to 6 mm. In the case of glass roving cloth reinforcement the glass contents of 8-plyed laminates were about 57 wt%. The glass contents of 8-plyed chopped strand mat-polyester laminates were ca. 30 wt%.

Test specimens

Dog-bone-shaped tensile specimens, conforming ASTM D638 type I, 12.6-mm wide and 165-mm long were prepared by cutting polyester plates with a band saw and by abrading with a belt sander. The tensile strength of the resins were measured with an Instron Universal Testing Machine Model 1114 with a grip separation of 115 mm and crosshead speed of 5 mm/min at 23 °C.

The plane-strain fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of neat resins were measured according to ASTM E399-81 and to Carisella's procedure with 3-point bending test specimen (1). The specimen dimension was 6-mm thick, 12.5-mm high and 80-mm long. The specimen was 4.5-mm deep notched with a band saw followed by the introduction of sharp crack by tapping with sharp cutter blade at the base of the notch. The fracture toughness of the resins was measured with Instron Model 1114 with 5-mm span and crosshead speed of 1 mm/min at 23 °C. The fracture toughness of each specimen was calculated from the maximum load.

The 4-point bending FRP specimens with 20-mm wide and 130-mm long were prepared from glass roving cloth reinforced polyesters. The 4-point bending strength was measured with Instron Model 1114 with a support span of 102 mm and a load span of 34 mm at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min at 23 °C. The 3-point bending strength of FRP was measured with specimens having dimensions of 20- or 22-mm wide and 110-mm long, with 80-mm span and crosshead speed of 5 mm/min.

The numbers of the specimens used for each measurement were 2 to 6 for tension, 4 for 4-point bending, 4 or 6 for 3-point bending, and 4 to 6 for fracture toughness. The results of the measurements were shown in the average and in the range.

Immersion tests

In order to evaluate the durability of FRP in humid environments for a long period, neat polyester resins and FRP were immersed in boiling water, and their residual strength were measured. The immersion test in boiling water were done both at atmospheric pressure and at slightly higher pressure by the use of a pressure cooker. At atmospheric pressure, the immersion vessels used were a conventional cooking kettle and a water bath with electric heater. The pressure cooker was 10 liters in volume, and the temperature of contained water reached to ca. 116 °C at an inner pressure of 0.18 MPa (Riken Light Metal Ind. Co.).

The specimens were immersed in boiling water and in the pressure cooker. After immersion for a certain time, the specimens were taken, quickly wiped and weighed. The specimens were put in a polyethylene film bag to avoid additional loss of water before mechanical testing. When the immersion test was repeated more than 8 hr, the specimens were kept in water for 16 hr. The mechanical properties of the immersed specimens were measured in a similar manner to that without immersion. As the immersed specimens for the fracture toughness had only saw cut, a sharp crack was introduced just before testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of various additives on glass roving cloth-orthophthalic polyester laminates

An orthophthalic polyester was modified with various additives in order to improve the corrosion resistance of FRP in humid environments, for orthophthalic polyester was most popular as the matrix of FRP and relatively inexpensive. These modified matrices and glass roving cloth were used for the preparation of FRP laminates.

Fig. 1 shows the weight changes of these FRP after immersion in boiling water. The immersion of FRP for 8 hr resulted in the weight change of about 0.4 %, while duration of total immersion time to 24 hr led to ca. 0.6 % of weight gain. In the cases of AGE, GMA and Vase addition, the weight change was larger than that without additive. While in the cases of MMA and St, the weight gain was smaller than that of no additive.

Fig. 2 shows the 4-point bending strength of FRP before and after immersion in boiling water. The 5 phr addition of GMA, MMA and St was effective for the 10-15 % improvement in flexural strength both before and after immersion. However, the percent retention of the flexural strength after boiling water immersion, decreased in a similar manner to that of no additive. These results are useful in practical FRP production. In order to improve impregnation of a matrix into glass fiber bundles, and to reduce unfavorable void formation, some additives are occasionally necessary to lower the viscosity of the resin.

Effect of boiling water immersion on polyester resins

As a matrix is responsible for the corrosion resistance of FRP, the immersion tests were done for 4 types of neat polyesters. Fig. 3 shows the weight gain of polyesters after immersion in boiling water and after heating in the pressure cooker. In any resins the weight change increased in the order: boiling water 8 hr < pressure cooker 8 hr < pressure cooker 8 hr x 3. The weight gain of the resins decreased in the order: O-resin > I-resin > V-resin > B-resin. The weight change of O-resin was remarkable, and total immersion time of 24 hr in the pressure cooker resulted in weight gain of 3.3 %.

Fig. 4 shows the tensile strength of neat resins after immersion in boiling water. In any resins the strength decreased in the following immersion conditions: boiling water 8 hr > pressure cooker 8 hr > pressure cooker 8 hr x 3.

The strength reduction of O-resin was particularly enormous as a result of 24-hr heating in the pressure cooker. In other resins the strength decreased gradually with increase in the immersion time.

Fig.5 shows the fracture toughness of neat resins before and after immersion. The fracture toughness was in the decreasing order of V-, O-, I- and B-resins. The fracture toughness of V-resin was particularly larger than that of other resins, indicating that this material could be used as structural parts with much safety. It was surprising that the heating in boiling water by use of the pressure cooker did not change greatly the fracture toughness of these resins, though large weight gain and the reduction in tensile strength were recognized in them. These phenomena were particularly evident in O-resin, for the tensile strength of this resin dropped remarkably by the immersion in the pressure cooker for 24 hr. By the visual inspection of 24-hr immersed O-resin, the edges of the tensile specimen were cracked slightly and a few small voids were formed on the surface. The tensile strength of a material usually decreases by the formation of flaws or voids. In the fracture toughness measurement a sharp crack was introduced before testing and the stability of this cracked specimen was tested. As the crack tip was sharper than the voids or flaws formed in the immersion, the fracture toughness of immersed resins must be unchanged.

Effect of boiling water immersion on chopped strand mat-polyester laminates

As the effect of the boiling water immersion on the properties of neat polyesters had been investigated, the accelerating immersion of FRP prepared by these matrices was examined. Fig.6 shows the weight change of chopped strand mat-polyester laminates after immersion in boiling water and after heating in the pressure cooker. In this figure O-FRP, I-FRP, V-FRP and B-FRP represent the FRP prepared by O-, I-, V- and B-resins, respectively. The feature of Fig.6 is similar to that of Fig.3, though in the cases of FRP the amount of weight gain was smaller than that of neat resins. In any FRP the weight change increased in the order of boiling water 8 hr, pressure cooker 8 hr and pressure cooker 8 hr x 3. The weight change of FRP was depended on the matrix and this value decreased in the order of O-, I-, V- and B-FRP.

Fig.7 shows the 3-point bending strength of chopped strand mat-polyester laminates before and after immersion in boiling water. The reduction in the flexural strength of O-FRP after immersion in boiling water by use of the pressure cooker, was not so large, though neat O-resin showed considerable drop in the tensile strength. The finding that the reduction in flexural strength of FRP after immersion was not so large as expected from the behavior of the polyesters, could be explained as follows. In chopped strand mat-polyester laminates, the glass fibers aligning to the stress direction still sustain a load thus the reduction in the strength of immersed FRP was small.

Comparison of the immersion between in boiling water and in pressure cooker

In the preceding sections the immersion test of resins and FRP were examined both in boiling water and in the pressure cooker. It is interesting to examine how much extent the pressure cooker was useful to evaluate the degradation of FRP in humid environments. Fig.8 shows the results of the comparison between the two immersion tests. The immersion of I-FRP in boiling water for 24 hr corresponded to 5-8 hr immersion in the pressure cooker on the basis of weight change and strength reduction. The 48-hr immersion in boiling water corresponded to the immersion in the pressure cooker for ca. 16 hr. The quality checking of FRP in boiling water immersion for 24 hr might be replaced by the use of a pressure cooker within 8 hr, accompanied by the saving in time and energy.

REFERENCES

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Fig.1. Weight change of glass roving cloth-orthophthalic polyester laminates after immersion in boiling water.

Fig.2. Effect of various additives on flexural strength of glass roving cloth-orthophthalic polyester laminates.

Fig.3. Weight change of neat polyester resins after immersion in boiling water and after heating in pressure cooker.

Fig.4. Tensile strength of polyester resins after immersion in boiling water and after heating in pressure cooker.

Fig.5. Fracture toughness of polyester resins after immersion in boiling water and after heating in pressure cooker.

Fig.6. Weight change of chopped strand mat-polyester laminates after immersion in boiling water and after heating in pressure cooker.

Fig.7. Flexural strength of chopped strand mat-polyester laminates after immersion in boiling water and after heating in pressure cooker.

Fig.8. Weight change and retention of flexural strength versus immersion time for chopped strand mat-isophthalic polyester laminates.